

Catchment Investment Decision Support System

Computational approach

September 2020

V1: 07 June 2018 – Initial version

V2: 10 July 2020 – Updated parts of the document to include any changes and additions over the last two years

V3: 09 September 2020 – added more detail for computational procedures related to creating and revising intervention portfolios

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Introduction

This document summarises the key computational steps in the Catchment Investment Decision Support System (CIDSS). The purpose of this document is to provide;

- A basis for a review of the computational approach.
- Context for understanding why it works the way it does
- Context for interpreting output

Background

Catchment Investment Decision Support System (CIDSS)

The Seqwater CIDSS has been developed to support the planning and implementation processes for investing in the mitigation of catchment derived risks to the quality of raw water received at water treatment plants from 40+ catchments in south east Queensland. The CIDSS considers 50+ potential on-ground interventions and uses simulated annealing to optimise their implementation based on most efficient reduction in risk to drinking water quality from sediment and microbial pollution. The CIDSS allows the post processing refinement of optimal scenarios.

What does the CIDSS need to do?

The CIDSS needs to produce an optimised collection of interventions which provide the greatest reduction in risk at water treatment plants for a given dollar budget.

Boundary Conditions – what must be in the CIDSS?

- Must be risk based.
- Must be treatment plant specific.
- Must be able to work with incomplete data.
- Must handle suspended sediment threats.
- Must handle microbial threats (Bacteria, Protozoa, Virus).

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- Must be structured to be able to incorporate more threats in the future.
- Must be able to include more interventions in the future.
- Must be able to easily update the efficacy of different interventions.
- Must be computationally efficient (<1 hr scenario run times).
- Must have an interface that can communicate the result to the whole of Seqwater.
- Must be able to be set up and run from a graphical user interface.
- Must be hosted in a secure environment.

What is the CIDSS

The Seqwater Catchment Investment Decision Support System (CIDSS) is a planning support tool with a simulated annealing optimiser and is designed to produce a solution set of intervention activities across source water catchments providing the greatest reduction in drinking water quality risk for a given budget. The CIDSS is conceptually simple, but computationally complex. The underlying architecture of the CIDSS allows for a range of input threats which may change over time or by source water catchment. The CIDSS architecture also allows for the consideration of different intervention options over time and potentially different interventions for each source water catchment.

The CIDSS considers four main hazards (Total suspended sediments (TSS) and pathogens bacteria, protozoa and virus) each with numerous generation sources or processes (hazardous processes), and optimises the placement of 49 different water quality improvement interventions across 1,445 spatial planning units, spread across 33 source water subcatchments supplying 28 Water Treatment Plants (WTP).

Hazard: a focus of risk in water quality delivery which is managed at the water treatment plant and via on-ground interventions. The hazards in CIDSS are; TSS, Bacteria, Protozoa, and Virus.

Hazardous process: an activity which can be measured and potentially measured that produce hazards.

The hazardous processes for TSS source include:

1. Streambank erosion,
2. Gully erosion
3. Diffuse hillslope erosion,

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4. Landslides,
5. Point sources (eg, quarries, intensive livestock holding pens), and
6. Unsealed roads

There are six different hazardous processes related to the source of pathogens:

1. Onsite Sewerage Facilities (OSS)
2. Sewerage Treatment Plants and pumping stations (STP)
3. Stormwater discharge,
4. Effluent from Intensive livestock industries (point source), and
5. Livestock grazing (diffuse source).
6. Recreation

Each of the pathogen related hazardous processes can generate sources of bacteria and protozoa hazards whereas, human waste sources (OSS, STP, SW and recreation) can also generate virus hazards.

The principal of calculating risk at the water treatment plant is the same for TSS and pathogen hazards. The approach is to determine the total load of the hazard at the water treatment plant, then convert that load into a risk at the water treatment plant based on the capacity of the treatment plant to remove the hazard.

Risk = consequence x likelihood. The CIDSS considers a very long timescale (e.g. 100 years), in which case, likelihood = 1. Hence risk = consequence. The determination of risk is based on a hazard-consequence table developed for each water treatment plant for each of the four hazards (TSS, bacteria, protozoa, virus).

The a-priori weighting Vs Pareto front trade off to optimisation

There are two basic approaches to multi-objective optimisation;

Pareto front approach. This approach essentially creates multiple 'optimum' solutions, usually by focusing the optimisation on a single parameter objective function. This approach is computationally cumbersome because the optimisation must be run several times to create the pareto front. It is typically used in academic applications where there is a poor understanding of the relative importance of trade-offs or where it is difficult to convert the objectives to a common currency.

a-priori weighting approach. This approach creates a single objective function to focus the optimisation by combining the multiple objectives into a single focus objective. The difficulty with the approach is that a method of combining objectives needs to be developed and applied. The CIDSS considers TSS hazards measured as Tonnes/y of sediment as well as pathogen hazards which are measured as Coliforming units (CFU). The challenge is combining TSS and CFU into a single objective function to optimise. Fortunately, Seqwater operate in a 'risk paradigm' whereby the organisation is familiar with converting hazards into an equivalent risk in order to compare and prioritise intervention. The CIDSS adopts this risk-based approach, thereby hazards are converted to a risk, which then allows multiple disparate hazards to be combined into a single objective function (risk).

General approach to risk calculation

The TSS hazards are quantified as tonnes/y, whereas the pathogen related hazards are quantified as coliforming units (CFU). To conduct an optimization across these requires equivalent units to compare between hazards. The basic approach of the CIDSS is to convert all input threats, to hazards and subsequently into an equivalent total 'risk' at the treatment plant. This 'threat-to-risk' conversion is via a four step process:

- 1) Attenuate the threat from the source planning unit to the plant (create hazard-at-plant for each hazardous process for each planning unit).
- 2) Sum the attenuated hazard-at-plant from all contributing planning units (e.g. total hillslope erosion value from all planning units delivered to the plant) to provide the 'total hazard at plant'.
- 3) Compare the total hazard at plant with risk thresholds for the particular hazard at the plant to get a risk at plant for each hazard.
- 4) Compare the risk from different hazards to give an overall risk at the plant (maximum of the risks).

This process of determining the overall risk at the treatment plant is repeated at every iteration of the optimisation process to calculate the risk after an intervention is applied. This process is also applied on the initial and final state to generate the initial and result risk scores.

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Computational process overview

The basic architecture of the key computational stages, input and transitional data sets is summarised as four key stages (Figure 1):

- 1) Prepare the data to create a planning unit based layer representing the current (or revised) hazards at the planning unit. The pathogen input data is site based, this data needs to be converted to account for the collective hazard at a planning unit level. The method of converting from site to planning unit level is different for each microbial hazard.
- 2) Convert the hazard at the planning unit to a risk at plant. This is done by applying an attenuation to account for reductions in the hazard due to travel times and to then convert the collective hazard from all planning units to a risk at plant. The water treatment plant specific hazard-to-risk conversion creates a risk for each of four hazards (TSS, bacteria, protozoa and virus). These are combined to give a single overall risk value.
- 3) The optimisation function compares the dollar cost with the risk reduction for each iteration and according to the optimisation settings chooses whether to keep or reject the most recent scenario.
- 4) The intervention scenario creation process is based on the performance of the cost function element. The interventions are applied across all planning units for all interventions and the efficacy of the interventions is applied to produce revised raw input layers.

The subsequent sections describe the underlying processes for each stage of the computation.

Figure 1: Basic computational steps of the CIDSS

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Data preparation

The data preparation phase converts data from its input form to a table which represents the hazard at the planning unit for each input hazardous process. For TSS related hazards, the input data is presented as t/yr at the planning unit scale, so no transformation of TSS data is required.

For pathogen threats, the input data is in the form of site-based tables which list each activity for each hazardous process (e.g. onsite wastewater treatment plant, or individual farming enterprise) for each planning unit. The “Pathogen hazard transformation from site to Planning Unit hazard” (grey box in Figure 2) converts and determines the overall load (coliforming units) for each activity for each hazardous process for each planning unit.

The site based hazard for each pathogen hazard (bacteria, protozoa, virus) is modified based on the sanitary survey method of reducing the hazard based on the likelihood. These pathogen loads are converted to non-log (natural) domain, then each pathogen hazard for all sites within the planning unit are summed for each hazardous process. The hazardous process totals for each of the three pathogen hazards are then summed across all the hazardous processes to give a total pathogen load for protozoa, bacteria and virus for the planning unit. The total values are then converted to the \log_{10} domain.

Figure 2: Step 1 Prepare data

$$modifiedthreat = threat - (5 - likelihood)$$

Risk at Plant

The CIDSS is focused on reducing the risk from source water pollution at the water treatment plant (Figure 3). The first part of this process is to calculate the effective hazard at the plant by applying an attenuation factor to allow for distance travelled and dam capture (travel time/residency). The second step in the procedure is to convert from the raw hazard units to a measure of risk at the plant.

Figure 3: Step two is to determine the risk at the plant

Hazard Attenuation

The hazard generated at the planning unit is transformed to an equivalent hazard at the water treatment plant by attenuating the load. The hazard attenuation process is different for TSS and pathogen hazards:

TSS hazard attenuation:

The TSS attenuation calculation is a three-part calculation:

- 1) Disconnected distance (distance from planning unit to stream network)

A ‘half distance’ for the hazardous process (typically similar for all TSS hazardous processes) is applied to the disconnected distance to determine the hazard attenuation due to traveling overland from the planning unit to the stream network. The reason that each hazardous process has the capacity to use different attenuation properties is to allow the distinction between hazardous processes that may be well connected to the stream network such as stream bank erosion, compared to landslides which may occur in isolated locations that are poorly connected to the stream network.

The half distance approach is analogous to a radioactive half-life, the half distance is the distance required to reduce the threat magnitude by half.

- 2) Connected distance (distance from planning unit to water treatment plant along the connected stream network)

The connected distance approach is an identical ‘half distance’ approach to that applied for the disconnected distance. The half distance represents the distance require to permanently reduce the

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TSS load by ½. The CIDSS is not a timestepping model, there is no accounting for temporary storage in bed and banks. The attenuation parameters should represent the permanent long-term reduction in load through processes such as overbank storage / floodplain deposition.

3) Trap efficiency (0-1 permanent trap efficiency of water storages).

The trap efficiency is used to account for permanent removal of sediment through capture in a reservoir. A trap efficiency of 1 means 100% of TSS is permanently captured between the planning unit and the treatment plant.

Table 1: An example application is for a TSS load from a planning unit of 10t/y. The resulting attenuated TSS at the plant would be 4t/y.

	Scenario level global values	For planning unit 1	TSS after attenuation
Disconnected half distance	0.5km	0km	10t/y
Connected Half Distance	30km	30km	5 t/y
Trap efficiency		0.2	4t/y

The attenuation properties (disconnected half distance and connected half distance) are specified at the ‘global’ level and apply to all planning units in a scenario. The planning unit specific attenuation parameters are the disconnected distance, connected distance and trap efficiency.

Pathogen hazard Attenuation

The raw data for microbial hazard is count based data (e.g. number of intensive agricultural farms, number of unsewered residences). The ~~count based~~count-based data is converted to a load of organisms (e.g. coliforming units for bacteria) value for each type of pathogen - bacterial, protozoa and virus for each of the pathogen hazardous processes;

1. onsite wastewater (unsewered residences),
2. pumping station overflow
3. stormwater
4. industry
5. agriculture (intensive agriculture)
6. Recreation

The method of converting the ~~count based~~count-based information to load of organisms for each of the 18 pathogen hazards is by using the Seqwater sanitary survey computational methods.

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The load of organisms at a planning unit is attenuated to a load of organisms at the water treatment plant based on the distance of different stream conditions between the planning unit and the treatment plant. The basic premise of the load of organism reduction relates to the residence time (Table 2).

Table 2: Factors and rates for attenuating pathogen scores along the flow path from Planning Unit outlet to water treatment plants (WTP).

Feature	Characteristic	Attenuation rate (specified at the Global scenario level)	Method
Large dam	Storage > 1GL	2 log / large dam	2 log for each Dam_name > 0
High discharge channel	Daily Q > 3 m ³ s ⁻¹ for > 70% of days per year	1 log / 50 km	0.02*Dist_HiQ
Low discharge channel	Daily Q ≤ 3 m ³ s ⁻¹ for > 70% of days per year	1 log / 10 km	0.1 * Dist_LoQ

The pathogen load of organisms values are attenuated for each pathogen hazard to produce a load of organisms at the treatment plant for each hazard. The attenuated microbial hazard for each planning unit is transformed to the natural domain and summed for each planning unit. The final sum of microbial load at the water treatment plant is then logged, ready for determining the risk at water treatment plant.

The attenuation properties (Attenuation rate for dams, high discharge channels and low discharge channels) are specified at the 'global' level and apply to all planning units in a scenario. The planning unit specific attenuation parameters are the number of large dams, the length of high discharge channel and the length of low discharge channel.

Converting threat to risk

The conversion of attenuated hazard to risk is similar for TSS and microbial processes.

TSS hazard to risk conversion

The TSS hazard to risk conversion is by a lookup table. The total at-plant TSS hazards are summed across all TSS hazards. This gives a total Tons per year of TSS delivered to the plant. The hazard to risk conversion applies a lookup process to assign a different risk for different TSS load totals.

The hazard to risk lookup table is water treatment plant specific and relates to the capacity to treat TSS. The method of generating the lookup table is outside the scope of the CIDSS.

Microbial hazard to risk conversion

The attenuated microbial hazards are summed across the planning units to give a total microbial load for each of protozoa, bacteria and virus at the treatment plant. Similar to the determination of TSS risk, the pathogen risks are determined from a hazard to risk lookup table.

Table 3: Example of hazard to risk conversion table

Risk	Descriptor	TSS	Virus	Bacteria	Protozoa
1	Insignificant	320	3	3	2.5
2	Minor	343	4	4	3.5
3	Moderate	521	5	5	4.5
4	Major	906	6	6	5.5
5	Catastrophic	2070	8	8	7.5

Categorical to continuous risk characterisation

In order to undertake the optimisation routine, small variations in hazard need to be assessed in order to accept or reject the small change in intervention portfolio. The categorical risk levels (1-5) does not allow a basis for assessment when changes occur within a risk category. To overcome this limitation, the CIDSS applies a continuous linear function within each risk category. This approach allows for comparison of alternative intervention portfolios. A special case is how to assign a continuous risk value when one is in the highest risk category (5). This category does not have an upper bound from which to draw a continuous linear function. The approach used by CIDSS is to set a 'level 6 risk' with a magnitude of the maximum hazard load (Figure 4).

A known issue with the approach adopted is that if the maximum hazard load is much larger than the level 5 risk hazard threshold, then the slope of the risk profile will approach horizontal, and very large changes would be required in the hazard load to result in a significant change in the risk level. In order to investigate these cases of single very large hazard loads, the CIDSS can be run in 'load' optimisation mode. When run in the load mode, the optimisation focuses on maximising load reduction per \$, which effectively relies on a linear function of load rather than a step function at each risk level.

Figure 4: Example of the assumed linear continuous function between risk levels.

Overall Risk

In order to create a single objective function to control the optimisation, the four risk values (TSS, protozoa, bacteria, virus) need to be combined to a single value. The risk values are combined based on a weighted average. The weightings of the relative importance of each of the four hazards are defined by the user as the ‘hazard weighting’. The default setting is an equal (25%) weighting across the hazards.

The hazard weighting approach applies in both the risk and load optimisation modes.

Optimisation function

The CIDSS uses a simulated annealing approach for the optimisation. The basic principal of the optimisation is to determine the overall reduction in risk or hazard load from the initial base case and to compare that to the cost of producing the risk or load reduction. The optimisation process and intervention portfolio generation process will be considered together in this section.

The general steps in the optimisation operation are:

1. Base run – determine the base risk (or load) from which to determine change for optimisation.
2. Run 0 – create an initial intervention portfolio.
3. Subsequent runs – create a ‘test’ portfolio of interventions by applying small changes (randomised) in the intervention portfolio from the previous run (near neighbour approach).
4. Determine risk or load at the treatment plant from the test intervention portfolio (call the ‘run-once’ routine).
5. Consider the results of the test (change in risk or load from base case) and accept or reject the test intervention portfolio.
6. If accepted, the test portfolio is stored as the ‘best’ portfolio, and subsequent refinement will be applied to this portfolio.
7. Return to step 3 and repeat until the maximum number of iterations is reached (usually ~1,000).
8. Prepare final results for data visualisation from the final ‘best’ portfolio.

Figure 5: optimisation function

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Optimisation method

CIDSS uses a third party simulated annealing computation library called Simanneal see <https://pypi.org/project/simanneal/>. The simulated annealing process involves:

1. Randomly **move** or alter the **state**
2. Assess the **energy** of the new state using an objective function
3. Compare the energy to the previous state and decide whether to accept the new solution or reject it based on the current **temperature**.
4. Repeat until you have converged on an acceptable answer

For a new scenario to be accepted, it must meet one of two requirements:

- The scenario causes a decrease in state energy (i.e. an improvement in the objective function)
- The scenario increases the state energy (i.e. a slightly worse solution) but is within the bounds of the temperature. The temperature exponentially decreases as the algorithm progresses. In this way, we avoid getting trapped by local minima early in the process but start to hone in on a viable solution by the end.

The parameters required to control the simulated annealing process are:

- Tmax – the maximum starting temperature
- Tmin – the ending temperature
- Steps – the number of iterations in the simulation
- Max_saturated_Steps – the maximum number of iterations to consider from a point determined to be close to a solution.

The key element of the simulated annealing approach is the logarithmic decline in ‘temperature’ and consequently the increased likelihood of accepting an improved scenario (lower energy) as the number of steps grows.

The basic cooling formulas are:

`Tfactor = -math.log(Tmax / Tmin)`

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`T = Tmax * math.exp(Tfactor * step / Steps)`

The energy is the cost function and the comparison as to whether to keep or reject a portfolio configuration is based on the change in energy (dE) divided by the temperature at that iteration step. The energy for a given iteration is the combination of the reduction in risk from the base risk and the deviation of intervention cost from the target budget.

$$(\textit{optimise for risk}) \textit{ energy} = \frac{[\textit{interventionCost} - \textit{budget}]}{[\textit{riskAfterIntervention} - \textit{baseRisk}]}$$

$$(\textit{optimise for load}) \textit{ energy} = \frac{[\textit{interventionCost} - \textit{budget}]}{[\textit{loadAfter} - \textit{loadBefore}]}$$

dE = energy for this portfolio – energy for previous best case portfolio.

In order to determine whether to accept a new portfolio, the energy must be lower than the previous best case and the exponent (base 10) of the -dE/Temperature must be greater than a random value between 0-1. The random value is selected from an even distribution. The temperature value decreased logarithmically across the iteration (creating a smaller $\text{math.exp}(-dE/T)$ value for a given dE as the optimization progresses. However, to ensure the method is not a simple hill climb strategy, this is compared to a random upper bound. As the optimization progresses there is a decreasing chance of rejecting an improved portfolio, and the optimization will approach a hill climb strategy.

`Reject if dE > 0.0 and math.exp(-dE / T) < random.random()`

Figure 6: cooling rate using the default CIDSS optimisation settings

Risk Vs Load objective function

The basic premise of the CIDSS is to optimise the reduction in risk per dollar value. However, in the case of extremely high loads, application of all interventions may not result in a reduction in risk level, hence the optimal solution is to do nothing (\$/risk reduction is minimised). In order to investigate these scenarios further, the CIDSS also has a 'load reduction' optimisation mode. In this case the optimisation objective function is \$/load reduction. The load reduction is simply represented as a proportional reduction for each hazard load and the overall load reduction is calculated using the weighted average approach. Even though this weighted average in load reduction is a dimensionless parameter, it may not make sense to consider load reduction in pathogens (usually considered in the log domain) alongside load reduction in TSS. The load reduction setting would usually be used when considering a single hazard.

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Intervention Scenario

The fourth and major component of the CIDSS is the creation and management of intervention portfolios (Figure 7).

Intervention Scenario

The intervention engine (grey box) creates an intervention portfolio. The intervention must be selected from within an upper and lower limit of interventions prescribed in the intervention upper and lower limits tables. These tables prescribe the maximum level of each intervention for each of the 40+ interventions for each planning unit. The default lower limit is zero. The purpose for the upper limit intervention is to ensure that a planning unit does not become ‘over subscribed’. For example an intervention which is focused on tree planting can only plant out that proportion of a planning unit which is not already vegetated. The reduction in load (and hence risk) due to applying interventions is by and efficacy approach.

Figure 7: intervention scenario

Hazard load reduction via efficacy approach

The computation of reduced hazard load due to applying interventions is achieved by an ‘efficacy’ approach. The efficacy approach assumes a proportional reduction in load from the hazardous process as the action is applied. For example, the intervention “River earthworks & fencing/less complex project (ES_RS_eart)” has an efficacy of 0.7 for TSS derived from hillslope processes, and 0.9 for TSS derived from channel sources. If 100% of the available area for this intervention is used, then the TSS generated from hillslope processes for this planning unit is reduced by 70% and the TSS load due to in channel processes from this planning unit is reduced by 90%.

The ES_RS_eart intervention has a unit of KM and has a cost per unit of \$250,000. The intervention ES_RS_eart has an implementation increment of 0.1. This implementation increment means that the optimisation could consider up to ten alternative levels of implementation of this intervention for every planning unit where there is capacity to apply the intervention. The efficacy is linearly scaled with the

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implementation increment. That is, for an efficacy of 0.7 and an implementation increment of 0.5, the load is reduced by 0.7×0.5 (35%).

For every planning unit, there is a record of the maximum level of every intervention that could be applied. For example, The Bea001 planning unit in the CGW catchment has a maximum stream length of 1.34km where the ES_RS_eart intervention could be applied.

Intervention Groups

Some land areas could have more than one intervention applied to them. For example, a length of stream may have a range of hard or soft engineering approaches applied to them, each with different levels of efficacy for different constituents and different costs associated with them. In order to address this condition of competing interventions, the CIDSS has the further concept of ‘intervention groups’. A group limit is set for all of the interventions in that group. For example, the ES_RS_eart intervention is part of a group of interventions ‘Stream Engineering (Strm_Eng)’. The stream engineering group includes:

- River earthworks /rockwork/ complex project (ES_RS_earc)
- River earthworks & fencing/less complex project (ES_RS_eart)
- River rockwork (ES_RS_roc)
- River rockwork & fencing/less complex project (ES_RS_rocf)
- Riparian earthworks – basic (AP_RZ_earb)

The group limits to intervention for the Bea001 planning unit in the CGW catchment is 1.34km. That is, any combination of the stream engineering group interventions cannot exceed 1.34km.

Pathogen efficacy approach

The efficacy approach represented as a proportional reduction in load described above applies to TSS. In the case of Pathogens (protozoa, bacteria and virus), the efficacy value is expressed as a log change in CFU. This alternative approach is to reflect the approach of the sanitary survey method whereby interventions are considered in terms of log reductions in CFU, not in percentage change. The implementation increments for interventions that target pathogens are whole units, this results in the combined log reductions per intervention implementation able to be additive, rather than determine a fraction of a log reduction.

A complicating factor for pathogen generating threatening processes is that the level of pathogen generation can vary for every site within a planning unit. For example, intensive agriculture sites close to a waterway can have a higher ‘likelihood’ component, and as such present a higher potential pathogen load. The approach to applying interventions to pathogen generating activities is to address each individual site within a planning unit. These sites are targeted from the highest load generation to the lowest load generation.

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The total pathogen load generated from a planning unit (for each of protozoa, bacteria and virus) is calculated by converting the load generated from each site presented as a log value, to a natural base and then summing all the natural base loads before converting back to a log base representation of the total CFU load per planning unit. The total load from the planning unit then goes through the attenuation process to determine the equivalent CFU load at the water treatment plant.

Continuous interventions

Most interventions which target pathogens are applied on a per unit basis (either the action is applied or it is not) which allows the number of sites to be targeted by the intervention to be identified. However, there are some actions such as riparian revegetation that can be implemented as a continuous function (number of Km of stream) and provide a log reduction in pathogens per stream length. In order to apply these continuous interventions, the CIDSS firstly determines the total CFU reduction (e.g. number of km of revegetation x CFU reduction per km). The site based hazardous processes that generate those pathogens are then sorted from the highest to the lowest generation rates (across all pathogen generating hazardous processes). The sites are removed in order from worst to best until the total pathogen reduction achieved from the intervention is reached. The final step in the pathogen reduction often requires a 'partial' reduction. For example, if riparian revegetation may reduce bacteria by 1CFU per km and 10.4 km of intervention is applied, then a total of 10.4 log reductions can be applied. If each site (e.g. intensive agriculture) is generating 3 Log bacteria. Then the revegetation has the effect of removing three intensive agriculture operations, and reducing the pathogen delivery from a fourth from 3Log to 1.6 log (i.e. 3-1.4).

Creating a portfolio of interventions

Initial intervention portfolio

Traditionally, a simulated annealing approach would commence with a completely random solution, which is subsequently refined. However, because the solution space for CIDSS is so large, several options for generating and initial seed solution were investigated.

Tested and rejected (1): The early attempts at generating a seed solution was based on the principles of marginal cost abatement curve approach where interventions are ordered from most cost effective to least cost effective. An additional complication for the CIDSS is the non-linear risk-load relationship means that the selection of best configuration is non-trivial. The considerations are which hazard is contributing to the overall risk, and within that hazard, which individual hazardous processes are contributing to that hazard load. Additionally, there is a significant effect of attenuation, whereby high hazard loads at the source may be attenuated to produce a low hazard load at the water treatment plant. The solution to the attenuation problem is not straightforward because a single planning unit can affect multiple downstream water treatment plants, all with different levels of attenuation and different

treatment capacities. The overheads (computational time) of the MCAC approach far outweighed the benefits because of the non-linear risk-load relationships, attenuation and multiple nested receiving water treatment plants.

Tested and Rejected (2): The purest form of selecting an intervention portfolio would be to make an entirely random selection of interventions (constrained by intervention limits). This approach was implemented before the full data set was available. Once full data was available it became apparent that the possible intervention matrix is very sparse. That is, most interventions are not applicable in most planning units, meaning that most random selections needed to be rejected. This created an unnecessarily large computational overhead.

Adopted method: The adopted method is to first create a matrix which records which interventions can be applied in which planning units. This very sparse matrix is then used to create intervention portfolios.

The method of determining the initial intervention portfolio is further refined to focus the interventions when producing every subsequent intervention portfolio.

Method Summary: The basic approach is to create intervention portfolios by gradually increasing the amount of intervention (randomly across available interventions) until the target budget is reached. Once the target budget is reached, the optimisation continues for a maximum of ‘saturated_max_steps’ iterations by randomly altering the amount of each intervention (increase and decrease).

Initial intervention portfolio

The initial setup requires the generation of a matrix (termed Search_direction) with columns = interventions and rows= planning units (Table 5). The values in the matrix are 0 or 1 indicating where an action can be applied in that planning unit. In order to determine if an action can be applied in the planning unit requires consideration of what threat/s occur in each planning unit and which interventions address those threats. This process is essentially to multiply two matrices. The first (Threat_Mask Table 3) is hazardous process (columns), where the attenuated hazardous process is simply recorded as being present or absent (1,0) x planning unit (rows) and the second matrix (Efficacy_mask Table 4) is interventions (columns) x threats (rows).

Table 3: Threat_Mask (matrix of the presence of a hazardous process per planning unit)

Planning unit	TSS_Hill	TSS_Gully	TSS_Chnl	TSS_Lansl	TSS_PSS	TSS_URoad	Ag	Onsite	STP	SW	Ind	Rec
PU1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
PU2	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
PU3	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
PU4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Table 4_Efficacy_mask (matrix relating interventions to hazardous processes)

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Hazard	ES_RS_earc	ES_RS_eart	ES_RS_rock	ES_RS_rocf	ES_RS_vega	ES_RS_fenc	ES_RS_vegf	ES_GS_earc	ES_GS_eart	ES_GS_rock	ES_GS_rocf	ES_GS_gras	ES_GS_vegw
TSS_Hill	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
TSS_Gully	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
TSS_Channel	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
TSS_Landsl	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TSS_PSS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TSS_URoad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ag_Ecoli	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Onsite_Pr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
STP_Ecoli	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SW_Ecoli	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ind_Pr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rec_Pr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 5: Search_direction (matrix of which interventions are available for each planning unit)

Hazard	ES_RS_earc	ES_RS_eart	ES_RS_rock	ES_RS_rocf	ES_RS_vega	ES_RS_fenc	ES_RS_vegf	ES_GS_earc	ES_GS_eart	ES_GS_rock	ES_GS_rocf	ES_GS_gras	ES_GS_vegw
PU1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PU2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PU3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PU4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The resulting Search_direction matrix is sparse.

An intervention matrix is created by modifying the Search_direction matrix. The intervention matrix values represent the number of intervention steps (or units) to apply. Each intervention has a defined ‘step’ size, this step size is mostly 0.1, which represents implementing the interventions in steps of 10%. The process is to select for selecting the number of steps for each intervention is to identify a growth range and decrease range (bounded by the min and max intervention) and then randomly select the number of steps within this range.

Because the process works by focusing initially on growing the budget, the random selection of intervention amounts is weighted toward growing interventions.

inc_scale = 3xsteps

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$dec_scale = 2 \times steps$

For each non-zero value in the search direction matrix, two values are generated at each step. These represent the upper and lower bounds of the number of steps to consider for the intervention. They are bounded by the maximum and minimum allowable intervention defined in the input.

$Max_intervention_steps(i) = \min(seed(i) + \max(Search_direction(i), 0) * inc_scale, puMax)$

$Min_intervention_steps(i) = \min(seed(i) + \min(Search_direction(i), 0) * inc_scale, puMin)$

For the first iteration, the seed(i) value is the minimum amount of intervention that can be applied (this is mostly zero). For all subsequent iterations, the seed(i) value is the intervention steps from the previously run best case.

The upper and lower intervention steps are then combined to get the intervention steps (new seed(i)) for that iteration. The method is to start from the previous seed value and then increase / decrease the new seed value by applying a random scale to the range from the current seed to the Max_intervention_steps(i) and Min_intervention_steps(i).

$New\ seed(i) = seed(i) + \max(random, 0) * \max_intervention_steps(i) - seed(i) - \min(random, 0) * \min_intervention_steps(i)$.

Group limits

The intervention matrix generated above will ensure that the interventions are within the bounds allowed for each intervention. However CIDSS also has the concept of group limits, whereby there is an additional constraint on the total intervention for interventions within a group. For example, all interventions that target the riparian can only add up to the total available riparian zone.

To ensure interventions stay within the bounds of the group limits, the intervention matrix is examined to identify exceedance of the group limits. Where an exceedance is detected, each intervention in the group is scaled proportionally to ensure the total intervention in the group meets the group limit maximum intervention

Targeting interventions

For each iteration, a new Search_direction matrix is created (to determine where attenuated hazards still exist). After the initial iteration, all subsequent iterations include the following steps to better focus interventions. These steps include separate processes to focus Pathogen and TSS related interventions.

Pathogen focus

The log domain of pathogen hazards means that a single hazardous process (and site) can dominate all other processes, and as such, intervening in any other pathogen producing hazardous process will have no significant effect on reducing the pathogen load and the risk at the plant. The challenge is to ensure, the primary pathogen hazardous process is targeted, rather than a random selection.

The basic principle is to invest actions that reduce the highest load producing hazardous processes. A consequence of this approach, is that if there are no available actions for the highest load producing hazardous processes, then no intervention will be applied.

In order to ensure the highest load pathogen generating process is targeted, an analysis is conducted at a planning unit level and then at a catchment level. At the planning unit level (Table 67), the largest load (protozoa, bacteria, virus) for each pathogen source is identified (1 in Table 67). At a catchment level, The highest risk pathogen for each hazardous process is determined. The Threat_matrix (

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Table 8) includes values of 1 for the hazard-threat (e.g. Ag-bacteria) that is a maximum for that hazardous process for that planning unit, and is also the largest threat (e.g. bacteria) for that hazardous process across all planning units.

The revised Threat_matrix (

Table 8) is used to generate the Search_direction matrix which determines which interventions can be applied in this iteration.

An important consequence of this step is that if no interventions exist to address the most pressing pathogen hazard-threat, then no action will be applied. This ensures that investment is not wasted on secondary and tertiary activities that have little overall load reduction benefit. However, it does create results which may seem illogical at first inspection, such as when a zero budget is spent.

Table 67: Threat_matrix revised to focus on PU level highest pathogen load generating hazardous process

Planning unit	Ag			Onsite			STP			SW			Ind			Rec		
	Protozoa	Bacteria	Virus															
PU1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
PU2	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
PU3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PU4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0

Table 8: Threat_matrix revised to focus on catchment level level highest pathogen load generating hazardous process

Planning unit	Ag			Onsite			STP			SW			Ind			Rec		
	Protozoa	Bacteria	Virus															
PU1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PU2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PU3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PU4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

The application of pathogen interventions occurs at a site based level (sub-PU level), from the most polluting to the least.

The above process is repeated at each iteration because their can be la large change in load and consequently in risk by addressing one or two critical microbial hazards (due to the effect of operating in the log domain).

TSS focus

When a risk has been reduced to below minor (level 1), there is no value in continuing to intervene in that hazardous process. More investment will not lower the risk. In this instance the CIDSS weights toward reducing the amount of intervention. This is achieved by changing the sign in the Search_direction matrix (-1). This step is considered for each iteration by assessing the overall TSS risk level at the treatment plant.

Intervention limits

The maximum and minimum levels of application of an intervention are recorded as an input to the CIDSS. The reason for the minimum field is to capture the use case whereby there may be minimum economies of scale for implementing certain interventions. For example, for engineering earthworks, the project initiation costs may be high, and hence there is a minimum viable size for the project. The maximum levels of application represent the upper limit of an intervention that can be applied for a planning unit. There are additionally maximum group limits for groups of competing interventions. The intervention limits are presented in the units that are defined for the intervention. That is, where an intervention unit is km then the intervention limit is expressed in km.

Impact of budget

The CIDSS cost function is risk reduction per \$. However, there is an additional requirement that intervention portfolios should achieve a target budget. This is to allow for the common use case ‘what is

the best collection of interventions for \$x?”. If the optimisation focused purely on the risk reduction/\$, then a likely and common outcome may be to do nothing, or do a very small level of activity.

In order to maintain an approach of maximum risk reduction per dollar for a given budget, the CIDSS applies budget ‘cost penalty’ to the portfolio. If the cost of the intervention portfolio is close to the target budget, then the cost penalty is low, however as the intervention portfolio cost deviates from the target budget an increasingly high penalty is applied. This high cost penalty will result in the scenario being rejected for one that is closer to the target budget.

The concept of a cost penalty is straight forward, however parameterising the cost penalty required testing a series of alternative penalty functions. The implemented cost penalty approach is to affect the overall ‘energy’ (which in turn affects if the portfolio configuration is accepted or rejected). See the assessing iterations section below.

Assessing iterations

Each iteration of the function applies the intervention, reducing the threat’s load. Calculating a new set of raw threats, their attenuation and risk after the applied intervention, then passing that data to the cost function which calculates the total optimisation cost to verify if the optimisation remains within the scenario budget assigned. The basic cost function of the CIDSS is to provide maximum risk reduction per dollar, (cf = \$/risk_reduction).

Applying this cost function directly will yield a result of zero interventions for zero dollars. A further constraint is that the scenario is provided with a specific budget. The cost function applied by CIDSS applies a hefty penalty for deviation from the budget. In this way the cost function tries to force a solution that is close to the specified budget.

$$(\textit{optimise for risk}) \textit{ energy} = \frac{[\textit{interventionCost} - \textit{budget}]}{[\textit{riskAfterIntervention} - \textit{baseRisk}]}$$

$$(\textit{optimise for load}) \textit{ energy} = \frac{[\textit{interventionCost} - \textit{budget}]}{[\textit{loadAfter} - \textit{loadBefore}]}$$

A note on processing speed: Because of the basic requirement to be close to the budget the initial optimisation process is spent achieving a scenario close to the prescribed budget before exploring the solution space in the that budget range.

There is a final check at this stage to confirm if the optimisation is complete. A complete solution is when the required number of iterations have been run. This may not be the optimal solution.

Preparing data for visualisation

At the completion of the optimization process, the final portfolio of actions is stored, as is the hazard load as well as the attenuated hazard load (both before and after interventions are applied). The associated total risk at the plant is also stored. In order to visualise the relative spatial distribution of the initial risk and the risk after the portfolio of activities has been applied the CIDSS needs to disaggregate the risk at plant to provide a relative contribution to risk for each contributing planning unit.

The overall risk at the plant is determined through a weighted average of the four sub risks (TSS, protozoa, bacteria, virus), where the weighting is based on the user defined risk weighting. There is single planning unit level 'relative contribution to risk layer'. That is, the disaggregation is based on the overall risk at plant, not the sub risks. The challenge in disaggregation of risk to planning units is that not all hazardous processes are present in all planning units.

The basic approach is to rescale the at plant risk-threat table to a planning unit based risk-threat table then using the pu level risk-threat table to determine the local pu risk levels before applying a weighted average to determine the overall pu level risk.

The procedure for disaggregating risk to give a relative risk contribution is:

- 1) Determine the relative contribution to the attenuated load for each hazard (TSS, protozoa, bacteria, virus) for each planning unit.
 - Relative TSS contribution from PU1 = $\text{attenuated TSS load PU1} / \text{Attenuated TSS load at WTP}$
 - Relative Protozoa contribution from PU1 = $\text{attenuated Protozoa load PU1} / \text{Attenuated Protozoa load at WTP}$
 - Relative bacteria contribution from PU1 = $\text{attenuated bacteria load PU1} / \text{Attenuated bacteria load at WTP}$
 - Relative virus contribution from PU1 = $\text{attenuated virus load PU1} / \text{Attenuated virus load at WTP}$
- 2) Scale the Risk-threat thresholds for the water treatment plant to get an equivalent PU level risk-threat threshold.
 - $\text{pu TSS risk threat threshold} = \text{Relative TSS contribution from PU} * \text{catchment TSS risk threat threshold}$

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iteration producing updated results to preview. If these results are saved, then the final 'best case' results of the optimization are overwritten with the view and refine parameters.

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